

ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE OF A LEADER IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART

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Annotation: In recent years, the country has been taking comprehensive measures to raise the spiritual and educational level of our people, strengthen the material and technical base of cultural and art institutions, support the industry. In particular, the importance of the innovative component of culture at the state level has become the main goal of the New Uzbekistan. This article discusses the analysis of the image of a leader in the field of culture and arts.

Keywords: Image; field of art; treatment culture; component of culture.

Culture is a set of symbolic devices and works that define human activity and the importance of that activity. Culture can be expressed in activities such as music, literature, art, architecture, theater, cinema, and lifestyle. In anthropology, the term "culture" refers to products and their production, their aesthetic meaning, and the social relations associated with these processes. In this sense, culture includes the arts, science, and spiritual systems. The history of culture and art is ancient. Its roots go back to the time of the first associations of mankind. The first forms of association are interpreted in the scientific literature in the Stone, Bronze and Iron Ages. During this period, the cultural socialization of people arose from the need to ensure life, to determine its sustainable duration. In order to provide for the material aspects of life, people have learned to hunt, fish, plant crops, and attract the opposite person through various games and exercises. The training was continuous. The continuity and continuity of teaching has led to the formation of education as a separate field. So, the activity of the cultural sphere is the basis of education.

Prospective projects implemented in our country on the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in all spheres, large-scale creative work carried out on the ground are radically changing not only the way of life, but also the worldview of our people. Such a noble process can be seen in the high attention paid to the development of culture and art, to the creative people. In the last two years, about 20 decrees and resolutions have been adopted in this area. Efforts are being made to implement them. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 28, 2013 "On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is of special importance as an important document aimed at overcoming the existing problems and shortcomings in this area.

Therefore, in the words of the head of our state, if culture and art do not develop in our country, society will not develop. In addition, there are many historical examples of how the true effect of development is measured not by the level of wealth or power, but by the heights of national culture. For example, the British art historian FR Martin writes that "there have never been rulers in Central Asia who valued art and culture like the Timurids." In this sense, the initiative of the head of our state to develop a concept for the further development of national culture includes our thinking, attitude to life, the present and future of the nation and people, the spiritual maturity of the younger generation, the roots of our work to create a bright future.

An image is a specific synthetic image that appears in the minds of people in relation to a particular person, organization, or other social object, that contains information about the perceived object and encourages social behavior. Creating the image of a modern leader is his face, dress, heart, common sense, culture of manners, a person who perfectly masters the art of management, competence: human qualities such as knowledge, thinking, professionalism, intelligence, humility, kindness, beauty, morality, instruction and example, based on the traditions of teacher and

student, to raise the prestige of man, to raise his prestige, to gain respect. Means: verbal, kinetic, visual. Presenting the image of a leader is the first impression. Menconception, acceptance. Means: communication, smiling, shaking hands, calling by name, exchanging business cards, using humor in a friendly relationship, expressing words in the eyes.

The eyes are the mirror of the human soul. Strong, self-confident views are a strong image. Bringing innovation to others. Image management is the efficient use of time, writing, strict mood, excitement management. Means: ensuring a healthy lifestyle (at home, at work), maintaining balance between home, work, parenting, business trips, programming success in the mind, solving problems in a timely manner to prevent emotions, strengthening partnerships, increase labor productivity, a realistic approach to oneself and others, the development of a culture of overcoming emotional distress in the home, a positive perception of innovation, monitoring the elimination of various emotions, changing the direction of ideas, ie sometimes we can even call it the “rubbing” method.

As Jonathan Swift put it, "In society, a bright image isn't given to many, but most people can be liked." The art of public speaking plays a key role in the image. As Napoleon said, "Those who cannot control their speech cannot be leaders." The leader must know how to speak in front of the audience, whether it is a partner or a subordinate. In order to please your business partners in a 5-7 minute lecture, you should pay attention to the following:

- first, think with your mind.
- second, you need to quickly grasp the recommendations that the audience has given you. Don't say what you want to say. Sometimes you can focus on an issue that is relevant to your audience.
- third, focus on key points, show how much you know about real life, talk about people's living conditions and what they want to achieve in business, and so on.

- fourth, think logically.
- fifth, identify areas of focus in the report. It should be clear that the issues you have raised are the most important and need to be addressed. Be sure to mention why you think so.
- sixth, the audience needs to support your ideas.
- seventh, learn to draw the audience out of the impressions left by the speaker before you.
- eighth, you can say great things to your audience. For example, thank them for their cooperation and understanding. the louder you say it, the more people will interact with you.

The biographical features of a leader include his or her age, gender, socioeconomic status, and education. the average age of employees in an organization headed by a soup manager is often low. Youth (around 30-35 years old) is characterized by a propensity for these innovations and discoveries, creativity, fearlessness and adaptability to a changing environment. Unfortunately, in such an organization, older (over 40-45) employees are even viewed with suspicion. However, it turned out that at the age of 35-55 a person becomes a master of his profession, has a good knowledge of his field and has a passion for the invention. At the same time, it creates a calm analysis of the situation, a calm mood. Of course, it is difficult to say that all young leaders are proponents of advanced technology and prone to it, but young people are characterized by modernity. This, in turn, increases the likelihood that a young leader will resort to modern and advanced production methods. There is a saying among our people that even if you are old, you are still young. This means that a modern leader, regardless of age, should be a proponent of advanced technology and be able to introduce modern production throughout the organization. This is a transitional requirement.

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